

BM-5102: ORGANISATIONAL BEHAVIOUR

REFLECTIVE CRITIQUE REPORT

TITLE OF REPORT:

IMPORTANCE OF UNDERSTANDING & ACKNOWLEDGING THE DIFFERENCES IN
GENERATIONAL COHORTS TO IMPROVE THE WORKFORCE

RESEARCH QUESTIONS OF REPORT:

How Does The View Amongst Different Cohorts Effect Their Relationship?

How To Ensure Effective Communication Between These Generations?

What Are The Challenges That Arise From Those Differences In Group Dynamics?

20M1279

Reflective Critique Report

Introduction

Generational cohort, a social science topic that is prevalent especially for western countries. It is just as important like gender or social standards. In Brunei however, there is a lack of research on it. At the same time, through previous observations, this is one of the problems that Brunei's workforce are currently facing. This is the reason this topic was chosen for the individual report.

The report was originally researched-based, with interviews and questionnaires. But, due to Covid-19 and other unexpected reasons, there was a need to change the report into a systematic literature review report. This can be seen as a major setback as with the lack of data Brunei have on this topic. The initial hope was to make an exploratory study to this topic on Brunei, making it known that it is topic that is worth researching on.

As the final report was done as a systematic literature review, it further proves how data on Brunei needs to be collected to understand better and create a sound argument by using Brunei's own socio-cultural norm. The findings, however, added my interest more into the topic as there are correlations to what has been observed and case studies from other countries. The success of research on this topic may actually improve Brunei's workforce for the better, moving forward.

Body Paragraphs

Project goals and the attempt to achieve them

The initial project goal before changing the approach for the report consists of; picking out topics that interest me the most that relate to management theories and processes; understanding the topic from different perspectives (different parts of the world); understanding the topic within the Bruneian context; finding solutions that can be applied to Brunei and lastly; create a report paper that I enjoy doing. With the alteration of the method, only one project goal was unable to be met, trying to understand the topic within Brunei's socio-cultural norm.

During the process of selecting the main topic, there was no proper systematic method was used. It was only by looking through the titles provided by this module. Inputting several titles on search libraries such as Google scholar, emerald and science direct. Reading the abstracts of articles from the first few pages. It was honestly disheartening at first as throughout the searches, reading numerous articles for several days, nothing really comes up of interest. The main topic for the report actually stems from a conversation with my siblings on their experiences at work and with my previous experiences as well, generational cohort becomes the main topic.

Starting from that, it was not hard to find articles on the matter within the management perspectives and there are numerous search results from western countries. Other countries from Asia were found as well, although it was limited. This made me even interested in the topic to try and explore. The findings from those articles really do help to provide an insight on what should be done to remedy the problems that are caused by differences in the generational cohort, to try

and see if it is applicable for Brunei. The report itself, it was actually very enjoyable especially due to the fact that this topic really piqued my interest.

All in all, I do feel as though the work that has been put on, into the makings of the report has addressed the requirements of the assignments to the best of my abilities and constraints and open my eyes into what topics that I may want to research on further in the future.

What has been learned?

In this research topic, several management theories that were taught in this module and other modules can be seen being used time and time again. These management theories are needed to understand the inner workings of how people will react to a certain stimulus, whether it be external or internal. As the topic revolves on several different generations, several motivational theories were used to understand the different needs and wants of different generations and provide the reason why they act as they are. Through this report, it gives the real-life practical usage of those theories and this help to create a better understanding of them.

The theories of motivation were the main concept in this topic that help to find the root of the problem and ways of solving it. It is the responsibility of a manager to uncover this problem from its roots and try to solve it from where it stems.

Through the findings from the systematic literature review, most of the data uses the already existing concept of generational cohort and that is using their cultural norms and major past experiences. Several studies have stated how important it is to actually understand what the cultural norm is on the country of research, as it may be far different and this makes some of the data inapplicable. Although it can be noted that there are still a lot of commonalities, as such it was not entirely unusable.

Opinions on the project

Honestly, it feels as though I did not contribute much to this topic due to the fact that the collection of data was not allowed when this was the main reason why this research should be done in the first place as there is a lack of resource on it. I feel that I may perform better if we were allowed to collect data. On this report, the only thing that I have contributed is an insight into the topic and where are the main areas that should be looked upon when doing this research.

The project itself can be viewed as something important. Because in this day and age, all generational cohort can be observed throughout every sector and different line of work. Although I may be accidentally biased on my perspective seeing more of the problem that occurs due to the fact that I have experienced it, as well as those around me. But without a doubt, this research would still be highly useful regardless. On this report, even if I am satisfied with it. In overall, I wish more could be done to acquire the results and try to analyse it, to provide factual data to support my worries.

The Outcome

The outcome of this project was only a partial success. Again this is due to the fact that data was unable to be collected. Data from Brunei was needed to actually see if the theories actually supported it within the context of Brunei and the other would be trying to see things in the perspective of Brunei.

The reason why it was a partial success, as what has been mentioned, It still provides a good assumption to the overall picture. Although those assumptions may not be fully true, it still provides good information that may help in future studies. The findings found through the systematic literature review can be used for Brunei to some extent.

This will benefit future research to narrow their search and concentrate on what matters the most. Other than that, the success would help the entirety of Brunei's workforce, especially in knowledge transfer from the older generation to the younger generation to assure that transition are smooth and efficient.

In the case, if it was possible to acquire data, it can be assumed that the outcome will be a success and that if the recommendations were done correctly, it may help some organisation with their problem with frictions between generational cohort.

Strength and Weaknesses- Professional development

Through this report project, several strength and weaknesses are revealed, although there are things that I may know of already in the first place, but this project helps me to realise how impactful it was.

Looking into strengths first, the first prominent strength that helps with pushing through this project is my interest in the topic that provided the high level of motivation and willingness in regards to anything related with this project. As someone who actually does not like to read, due to the interest, I have read more in those short period of time that can be comparable to a normal year's worth of reading. Another strength that I think worth mentioning is my tendency to not being biased to a generational cohort. Being someone who is more of a pacifist, I do not like to take on any sides, while at the same time giving a generalised opinion that can benefit anyone. Especially with the research topic, it helps to not being biased, as every side needs to be understood, expressed and helped equally.

For weaknesses, it relates back to my lack of interest in reading. As I was reading the journals and articles, due to the lack of practice in reading, it took longer to finish and even than that does not guarantee an understanding of it. It takes a couple of passes to make sure I could understand the concept that has been stated within the articles. If I was better at reading, it would help in finding more articles and contents. At the same time is my proficiency in writing. I have realised that my style of writing tends to be informal and long-winded. This may cause some people to be confused when reading my report. Lastly is the lack of systematic processes in doing the literature reviews. This made it hard and consumes a lot of time as I have to re-read the articles again and again.

In general, my skill in writing a report is lacking. Although I have lots of points and ideas, it is cluttered and unorganised. The only way for me to improve is by trying to practice a more systematic process and doing it, again and again, to get used to it.

What can be done in the future

What needs to be done for future research is to create our understanding of the generational cohort within our own cultural norm and major past experiences. That is the first step that needs to be done to even start understanding the reasons why through motivational theories.

Exploration research that tries to uncover the specific identification of the generation cohort with respect to our own culture and major experiences is the first step before anything else. The result of this research will help with a further future report that ties in with their motivational factors and their differences with different cohorts. Those differences will then be used to look into what causes the friction between them and finally, that will benefit in finding the proper solutions.

What Use Are Reflective Reports to Students?

A reflective report is useful for the student to critically critique themselves in a professional way that is less demeaning. Some students may look down on themselves to a point that they lose their motivation. With reflective reports, however, the students are letting allowing those critiques to reach them and take them in, in a positive way. With this, it helps the student to develop themselves.

Conclusion

My experience with this report leaves me with a sense of slight disappointment as I did not manage to complete it due to its approach being changed. Nonetheless, it gives me useful knowledge that will help me in the future when I want to research on this topic further. As of now, I can say that this report is only the tip of the iceberg and I plan to uncover it fully.

This report project inspires me to do more research on this topic as in my opinion, it may help to transform the current norm in Brunei's workforce and make it better. In the hopes that with this, it may create a cascading effect that will make it better and better not just for the current topic, but other topics as well, such as unemployment, better efficiency and proficiency. I am hopeful that the future will be bright and people will work collectively, aiming for the best for everything and everyone as this is not just about us, we have to think that our actions will affect others and theirs' will affect every other person. It would be a good idea in the future to start with a pilot study on an organisation and slowly scale it up, until to the point that it becomes the norm.

Reference

Musa, S. F., & Idris, D. S. (2020). Addressing Issues of Unemployment in Brunei: The Mismatch Between Employers Expectations and Employees Aspirations. *International Journal of Asian Business and Information Management (IJABIM)*, 11(2), 88-101. doi:10.4018/IJABIM.2020040106